

MICROSCALE STUDY OF BIOFILM FORMATION AT THE OIL-WATER INTERFACE

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ABSTRACT

Improved understanding of the fundamental mechanisms that control the physical and biochemical interactions between bacterial communities and oil droplets will enable the reliable prediction of oil dispersion and contamination risk assessment in aquatic ecosystems. The research focus of this work is on the investigation and quantification of biofilm formation over an oily substrate at the single-droplet scale of observation. Preliminary results from visualization experiments are presented here for the growth of *Marinobacter hydrocarbonoclasticus* in a microfluidic chamber with weathered crude oil as nutritive substrate. Breakup of the oily phase to fine droplets of size ranging from circa 4 μm to 30 μm as well as extensive bacterial aggregation have been observed.

KEYWORDS: biofilms; microfluidics; crude-oil; biodegradation

1. INTRODUCTION

The recent Deepwater Horizon incident in the Gulf of Mexico exposed significant challenges towards controlling and cleaning oil spills that originate from deep-sea releases of crude oil. Among those challenges remains the elucidation and quantification of the physical mechanisms involved in the natural biodegradation of crude oil droplets by marine microbes. At the single-droplet level of observation, at least three microbial strategies have been proposed for promoting the uptake of hydrocarbons and other hydrophobic oily substrates (Bouchez-Naïtali et al., 1999). In a first strategy, planktonic bacteria release amphiphilic biosurfactants (e.g., rhamnolipids) in the aqueous medium (Cameotra and Singh, 2009). The biosurfactants accumulate at the oil-water interface and decrease the interfacial tension, thus increasing the interfacial area and the rate of oil solubilisation. If the biosurfactant concentration exceeds the critical micellar concentration, then oil-in-water micelles are also formed (pseudo-solubilisation). In a second strategy, the microbial cells possess extracellular, membrane-bound surfactants and oxidative enzymes, which enable them to firmly attach, emulsify, and extracellularly oxidize the oily substrate. In this case of direct interfacial uptake, the bacteria form *thin* biofilms (thickness of a few cell diameters) over the surface of oil droplets (Whyte et al., 1999). In a third strategy, individual or clustered microbes attach to the oil surface and secrete excessive amounts of extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) with a wide range of molecular weight (Klein et al., 2010). High-molecular-weight EPS allow the microbes to build a biofilm community over the oily substrate. Low-molecular-weight amphiphilic EPS function as surfactants which reduce the oil-biofilm interfacial tension and increase the interfacial area by the formation of depressions into the oily phase. In all three strategies, the surface active agents of biological origin are *presumed* to play multiple key roles. However, an accurate *quantitative* description of these processes is still missing and, especially in the case of biofilm formation, the current understanding of the transport of oily substrates *within* the biofilm remains unclear.

The general research focus in this work is on the investigation and quantification of physical interactions between marine bacteria and crude oil droplets at the single-droplet scale of observation (from several micrometers to a few millimeters). The primary scope is the development of controllable microfluidic platforms that permit minimally invasive visualization of microbe-scale

phenomena (locomotion, proliferation, clustering) and biofilm-scale pattern formation in controllable and reproducible *in vitro* environments, under flow conditions. Along this direction, preliminary experimental results on the formation of *Marinobacter* biofilms over crude oil droplets within a microfluidic chamber are presented in this paper.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Oil and bacterial sources

Crude oil sampled from the Deep Water Horizon spill, after the blowout of the Macondo well at the Gulf of Mexico, was used as the oily phase in all the experiments presented here. The crude oil samples were contained in stainless steel bottles and stored in the refrigerator at 4 °C. These oil samples were collected and provided by the University of Texas Marine Science Institute (Dr. Ed Buskey). Before the experiments, the oil was artificially weathered by heating at 90 °C for 3hrs, thus allowing the most volatile hydrocarbons to evaporate.

The marine bacterial strain *Marinobacter hydrocarbonoclasticus* was obtained from the ATCC stock (#49840) and used in all the experiments. Bacterial stocks were properly preserved at 4 °C with marine agar and at -20 °C with glycerol:marine agar (50:50 % v/v). Bacterial cultures (30ml) were aseptically prepared in 100ml Erlenmeyer flasks and incubated at 30 °C in an orbital shaker. Each flask was capped with a sterile cotton plug in order to facilitate the maintenance of aerobic conditions within the flask. On the basis of a standard agar-plate test, there is no indication for acute inhibitory effects of the weathered crude oil on the *Marinobacter* species, under conditions of direct exposure. Further, although this species is considered to be motile, no significant motility was observed either under the microscope or from the standard soft-agar stabbing test. Before the biodegradation experiments, the *Marinobacter* species was acclimatized to crude oil via a gradual transfer in the culture medium from marine broth to a synthetic salt water that contained crude oil (1 % v/v) as carbon source as well as mineral salts (w/v): 1.23% Tris, 0.37% NH₄Cl, 0.62% MgSO₄·7H₂O, 0.15% CaCl₂, 0.075%KCl, 3.5% NaCl (Gauthier et al., 1992).

2.2 Microfluidic device

The oil biodegradation experiments were conducted with the flow chamber presented in Figure 1. The construction of this device was made using a soft lithography procedure. In short, the pattern for the device was designed with AutoCAD 2013 and printed out on adhesive vinyl paper with a ROLAND GX-24 cutter. Then, the vinyl mold was adhered to the bottom surface of a Petri dish (polystyrene). A polydimethyl-siloxane mixture (PDMS, SYLGARD 184) was poured into the Petri dish and allowed to cure at 70 °C for 3hrs. The cured PDMS part was bonded to a clean glass slide right after exposure to air plasma in a HARRICK PDC-32G plasma cleaner. As a final step, the inner surface of the flow chamber was chemically treated with polyelectrolytes in order to become uniformly hydrophilic (Bauer et al., 2010) (this step is crucial because the surface of the PDMS part is originally hydrophobic). The depth of the fluidic chamber is 200µm. All the steps of the soft lithography procedure were performed inside a clean room facility.

Figure 1.
The microfluidic device used in the study of biofilm formation over oily substrates.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The preparatory procedure for the oil biodegradation experiments involved the following basic steps. First, the microfluidic device was chemically sterilized with a solution of isopropanol and deionized water (70:30 % v/v). Second, the isopropanol solution was flushed out by sterile synthetic salt water, and a sample of the bacterial culture was injected into the device. Then, the oily phase was injected at a very low flow rate (1 μ l/min) until an oily blob of desired size was formed in the device. After a waiting period of 30min with no-flow (for bacterial attachment), the injection of synthetic salt water was initiated and maintained at a constant flow rate (50 μ l/min) throughout the experiment. At certain time points, the device was transferred to the microscopy unit for visual observation of the biodegradation progress. The visualization was performed with a NIKON TiE inverted microscope equipped with an IMPERX ICL-B2020 CCD camera.

Figure 2. Microphotographs of *Marinobacter* aggregates (biofilms) over crude oil droplets that have been formed within the microfluidic device. (A) Cell-free as well as biofilm-encapsulated oil droplets of size circa 10 μ m; (B) Close-up of the biofilm-encapsulated droplets; (C) Biofilms and a "necklace" of ca. 4 μ m droplets (arrowhead); (D) Biofilm over a ca. 30 μ m droplet; (E) Biofilms and dispersed individual bacteria between them; (F) Heterogeneous biofilm with encapsulated 4 μ m droplets (arrowhead) observed after 1 week. All these microphotographs have been acquired with a Nikon TiE microscope operated at phase contrast mode and equipped with an Imperx ICL-B2020 CCD camera.

Selected microphotographs of the biofilm formations observed during the biodegradation of crude oil are presented in Figure 2. The following qualitative observations have been made:

- First, in this series of preliminary experiments, the bacteria did not form any detectable biofilm structure at the surface of the initial large oil blob. One plausible explanation for this observation might be that certain growth-inhibiting components of crude-oil (e.g., aromatics) were concentrated at the oil-water interface. This point requires further investigation.
- Second, the crude oil blob breaks down into fine oil droplets (4 μ m to 30 μ m) which disperse into the microfluidic device. Since no dispersant was added to the synthetic salt water, this pseudo-solubilization phenomenon implies that the *Marinobacter* releases surface active agents.
- Finally, the *Marinobacter* species tend to form large aggregates (biofilms) in the device and, in many instances, the bacterial aggregates were found to be attached to or even encapsulate fine oily droplets. At this point, it is not clear whether individual cells first attached to the droplets and then proliferated to form aggregates, or the oil droplets were captured by preformed aggregates.

4. FINAL REMARK

On the basis of the experimental observations presented in this work as well as relevant data from the literature, one concludes that the interactions between bacterial communities and oil droplets constitute a fascinating yet quite complicated process. Much further research is required in order to achieve an accurate description of this process on the grounds of first principles (and less empiricism). The multiple roles of biosurfactants must be taken into proper account in order to decipher and quantify the underlying physical mechanisms. In parallel to this experimental investigation, efforts are also made to model the formation of biofilms over the oily substrates using the computational framework developed previously by our group (Kapellos et al., 2015).

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